

Copper-, Cobalt- and Zinc(II) Complexes with Monofunctional Bidentate Schiff Base and Monodentate Neutral Ligands

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The transition metal complexes of oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands find many industrial and medicinal uses¹. The transition metal complexes having oxygen and nitrogen donor Schiff bases, possess unusual configuration² and structural lability. These complexes are sensitive to molecular environment. The number of monodentate neutral ligand coordination depends on the nature of the central metal ion. Generally, stable stereochemistry is obtained through dimerisation. So, the nature and geometry of a few complexes with stoichiometries M_2L_2L' and $M_2L_2L'_2$, where $M = Cu^{II}$, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} , L = monofunctional bidentate Schiff base (**1a**, **b**) and L' = monodentate neutral ligands having nitrogen as donor atom, are reported here (Scheme 1).

Results and Discussion

The complexes (**2-4**) (Table 1) are microcrystalline solids having high melting points and are insoluble in water but sparingly soluble in common organic solvents. The analytical data are consistent with the formulation of the compounds. The low molar conductance values of all complexes ($0.82-5.2 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) at room temperature suggest their non-electrolytic nature. The molecular weight values indicate that the compounds are monomeric.

The ir spectra of the Schiff base (**1a**) show two strong and broad bands at ~ 2860 and 3290 cm^{-1} attributable to ν_{OH} and *cis*-form of ν_{NH} modes respectively³. Bands appearing at 3385 and 3460 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu_{asym}(\text{NH})$ and $\nu_{sym}(\text{NH})$

respectively of the NH_2 functional group of **1a**^{3,4}. The $\nu_{C=N}$ band of **1a** appearing at $\sim 1610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was shifted to higher frequency region ($1620-1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) on complexation indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen⁴. A strong band observed at 1670 cm^{-1} corresponds to $\nu_{C=O}$ mode of **1a**^{4,5}. On complexation this band disappeared indicating enolisation of **1a** and its chelation through

enolic oxygen⁵. This is further supported by the appearance of ν_{C-O} band at $1\ 350 \pm (10-20)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. Thus **1a** behaves as a monofunctional bidentate (O, N donor) ligand⁵⁻⁷. The presence of coordinated pyridine is known from its $\nu_{C=N}$ band observed at $1\ 640 \pm (10-20)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes^{6,7}. Similarly, the coordination of 4-methylpyridine is confirmed from its $\nu_{C=C} + \nu_{C=N}$ bands observed at $1\ 530-1\ 540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes⁷. The other bands were masked by **1a** bands. The bands appearing at $1\ 570-1\ 590\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=N) of quinoline and isoquinoline support their coordination to the metal ions through the nitrogen atoms^{7,8}.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-4

Compd. no.	M.p.(°C)/ (Colour)	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		M	N	C	H
1a, b	220 (Pink)	—	23.3 (23.4)	53.4 (53.6)	5.0 (5.0)
	2a	232 (Blue)	12.6 (12.7)	19.4 (19.6)	50.3 (50.5)
b		225 (Blue)	12.2 (12.3)	19.0 (19.1)	51.3 (51.5)
	c	240 (Blue)	11.4 (11.5)	17.6 (17.8)	54.6 (54.7)
d		238 (Blue)	11.3 (11.5)	17.7 (17.8)	54.5 (54.7)
	3a	222 (Purple)	10.0 (10.2)	19.4 (19.5)	54.3 (54.4)
b		248 (Pink)	9.6 (9.8)	18.5 (18.6)	55.7 (55.9)
	c	235 (Violet)	8.6 (8.7)	16.5 (16.6)	60.4 (60.6)
d		243 (Violet)	8.5 (8.7)	16.4 (16.6)	60.5 (60.6)
	4a	250 (White)	11.0 (11.2)	19.1 (19.3)	53.6 (53.8)
b		227 (White)	10.5 (10.7)	18.3 (18.4)	55.2 (55.3)
	c	242 (White)	9.5 (9.6)	16.3 (16.4)	58.8 (60.0)
d		249 (White)	9.4 (9.6)	16.3 (16.4)	58.9 (60.0)

The electronic spectra of **2a-d** were found to exhibit absorption maxima around $16\ 120-16\ 280\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which indicate the pentacoordinated stereochemistry^{9,10}. The strong bands at $16\ 500-20\ 700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in **3a-d** may be assigned to spin-allowed *d-d* transition of the type ${}^4A_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ suggesting high-spin hexacoordinated stereochemistry¹⁰. The results support octahedral configuration for **4a-d**.

The magnetic moment values of **2a-d** (2.01–2.18 B.M.) are consistent with $3d^9$ system^{11,12} and **3a-d** exhibit μ_{eff} values (4.79–5.11 B.M.) expected for high-spin octahedral Co^{II} complexes^{12,13}.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

4-Hydroxybenzal semicarbazone (1a-b) : The semicarbazide (8 g, 0.1 mol) was dissolved in hot water in presence of glacial acetic acid (3 drops) and sodium acetate solution (12 g in 80 ml water). To it, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (13 g, 0.1 mol) solution in ethanol was added, stirred for ~ 10 mins and kept for ~0.5 h to yield a light pink crystalline solid. It was filtered, washed with water, dried at 80° in an air-oven and crystallised from methanol. The Schiff base (**1a-b**) was found insoluble in water but soluble in common organic solvents.

Pyridinebis(4-hydroxybenzal semicarbazone)copper(II) (1a) : The solutions of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.9 g, 0.005 mol) and **1a, b** (1.8 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol, were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio and stirred on a magnetic stirrer for ~0.5 h. To it, an ethanolic solution of pyridine, 4-methylpyridine, quinoline or isoquinoline was added in excess with constant stirring. The resulting solid complexes were washed with ethanol, acetone and petroleum ether, then dried under reduced pressure; the Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were prepared in a similar way (Scheme 1) : yields 69–88%.

Molecular weights were measured by Rast's camphor method. Magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature by Gouy's method. Diamagnetic correction were made by using Pascal's constants¹⁴. The conductance measurement¹⁵ was carried out using $\sim 10^{-3}\text{ M}$ nitrobenzene solution of the complexes with a Toshniwal CL-01-06 conductivity meter. Infra-red spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR 408 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Shimadzu 160 spectrophotometer.

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NOTE

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